

Mentoring

Q1 We are a team of computer science researchers investigating the benefits of informal mentoring in open-source communities. Your input will help us identify how mentoring occurs implicitly in day-to-day tasks in open-source communities and its benefits.

This survey should take approximately 5-10 minutes to complete. The results of this survey will be used in a scientific publication. There will also be a question at the end of the survey for you to indicate if you would like to receive a copy of any publications or reports generated from this study. By clicking the button below, you acknowledge that your participation in the study is voluntary, you are at least 18 years of age, and that you are aware that you may choose to terminate your participation in the study at any time and for any reason. If you have any questions or concerns, please contact...

EEA Data Privacy: Participants in the EEA are advised that data privacy laws have not been deemed adequate by the European Commission. For more information, participants can contact...

I consent

I do not consent

Q2 How do you identify yourself?

- Woman
 - Man
 - Gender variant / Non-conforming / Non-binary
 - Prefer not to say
 - Prefer to self-describe (please answer as comment)
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Q3 How long have you been involved with open source software?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 2 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 6 to 10 years
- Over 10 years

Q4 What is your education level (or equivalent)?

- No formal education
- High school
- Technical training
- Undergraduate degree
- Master's degree
- Ph.D

Q5 Please identify which of these activities do you consider a part of mentoring: (select all that apply)

- Giving/receiving suggestions with an explanation
- Giving/receiving instruction with an explanation
- Helping address an issue/error and giving an explanation
- None of the above
- Others, please specify:

Q6 Do you agree with the statement: Implicit / informal mentoring occurs in everyday development activities? (e.g., code review)

Agree (2)

Disagree (4)

Q7 Please identify where implicit mentoring takes place: (select all that apply)

Email (1)

In person (2)

Pull-request comments on GitHub (3)

Comments on Stack Overflow (4)

Comments on issues list (5)

Others, please specify: (6)
